

Titrimetric Determinations using Iodine Trichloride in Hydrochloric Acid Medium

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Direct potentiometric and visual titration methods are developed using ICl_3 as the titrant for the determination of As(III), Sb(III), Tl(I), ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, hydrazine, semicarbazide, thiocyanate, Reinecke salt and sulphite. Also excess-back titrations are developed using ICl_3 for the determination of thiosulphate, thioacetamide, dithiocarbamate and its complexes with Cu(II) and Zn(II), xanthate and its complexes with Cu(I) and Zn(II), sulphides of Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II), thiosemicarbazide complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II), $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ and $\text{Hg}[\text{Zn}(\text{CNS})_4]$.

IODINE trichloride, ICl_3 , is one of the stable interhalogens used as redox titrants in aqueous and non-aqueous media¹⁻⁸. In this paper, we are reporting the results of our studies on ICl_3 for the determination of 26 reductants including soluble and insoluble compounds. Direct potentiometric and visual titrations using ICl_3 as the titrant are developed for the following reductants: arsenic(III), antimony(III), thallium(I), ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, hydrazine, semicarbazide, thiocyanate, Reinecke salt and sulphite. Excess-back titrations are developed for the following difficultly oxidizable compounds for which direct titrations are impossible: thiosulphate, thioacetamide, dithiocarbamate and its complexes with Cu(II) and Zn(II), xanthate and its complexes with Cu(I) and Zn(II), sulphides of Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II), thiosemicarbazide complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II), mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) and mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato zincate(II).

Experimental

Reagents :

Iodine trichloride : Decinormal solutions of ICl_3 in hydrochloric acid medium were prepared by the method of Fialkov and Kagan¹. 3.57 g of KIO_3 was dissolved in 100 ml hot water. After cooling, 1.38 g KI and 41.7 ml conc. HCl were added and the resulting solution was cooled to room temperature, diluted to 1 litre with water and stored in stoppered flasks. The ICl_3 solutions thus prepared were standardised by an iodometric procedure similar to that used for ICl_3 .

Reductants : Standard solutions of all the soluble reductants were prepared by the standard methods^{10,11}. The other insoluble reductants were prepared by the methods given in literature¹⁰⁻¹² and the finely powdered dry samples were used for the titrations.

Apparatus for potentiometric titrations :

A Toshniwal titration potentiometer type CL 06 with "magic eye" detector, magnetic stirrer, an aqueous saturated calomel electrode and a smooth platinum electrode was used for potentiometric titrations. The equivalence points were determined from the peaks of the first derivative curves and these were checked by the Hostetter-Roberts equation¹³ or the Yan equation¹⁴.

Procedures for the titrations :

Four types of titrations—potentiometric, direct visual using starch indicator, Andrews type (using CCl_4 as the partition indicator) and excess-back—are developed. The usual procedures are used for the four types of titrations.

Results and Discussion

Iodine trichloride reacts with any reductant other than KI according to the following equation :

For example,

This is a 4-electron transfer reaction and therefore, in direct titrations ICl_3 is reduced to iodide and chloride. However, ICl_3 reacts with KI according to the following equation :

This is a 3-electron transfer reaction. In back titrations, excess of ICl_3 is treated with the reductants and the unreacted ICl_3 is determined iodometrically (adding excess of KI). Therefore, in back

titrations, ICl_2 is reduced only to iodine and chloride.

Direct potentiometric titrations, direct visual titrations using starch indicator and direct Andrews type titrations using CCl_4 indicator are successful for the following 10 reductants: As(III), Sb(III), Tl(I), ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, hydrazine, semicarbazide, thiocyanate, Reinecke salt and sulphite. However, in the case of sulphite reverse titration procedures are followed in all the three methods i.e., sulphite solution is added from the burette to the standard ICl_2 solution containing other required reagent. The end-points in the case of sulphite are a fall in potential for the potentiometric method, disappearance of blue colour for visual method using starch indicator and disappearance of pink colour in the CCl_4 layer for Andrews method. In all the three direct titration methods, addition of HgCl_2 is essential for all the reductants excepting ascorbic acid and sulphite. The function of HgCl_2 , in these cases, is probably to remove the iodide formed during the reactions and hence to shift the reactions forward. In the cases of ascorbic acid and sulphite the iodide formed during the reactions may react with ICl_2 to form iodine, which in turn, can oxidise these two reductants very easily. Therefore, addition of HgCl_2 is not needed for these two reductants. In the cases of other reductants iodine is not a powerful oxidant and therefore, the formation of iodine is suppressed by removing iodide via complexation with HgCl_2 .

The remaining 16 reductants cannot be determined by direct titration methods and they are determined only by excess-back titrations. In excess-back titrations, addition of HgCl_2 does not make any difference at all, since ICl_2 is reduced only to iodine state here. The time intervals for completion of the reactions are different for these reductants. Thus a period of 30 minutes is needed for thiosulphate and thioacetamide; 1 hr for ZnS and CdS; $1\frac{1}{2}$ hrs for dithiocarbamate and xanthate and their complexes with Cu and Zn; and 2 hrs for CuS, thiosemicarbazide complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II), and mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato complexes of Co(II) and Zn(II).

As expected from their usual oxidation schemes, 1 equivalent of oxidant is consumed per mole of CuS; 2 equivalents for As(III), Sb(III), Tl(I), ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, sulphite, ZnS and CdS; 4 equivalents for hydrazine and semicarbazide; 6 equivalents for thiocyanate; 8 equivalents for thiosulphate and thioacetamide; 14 equivalents for dithiocarbamate, xanthate and Cu(I) xanthate; 20 equivalents for thiosemicarbazides of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II); 24 equivalents for Reinecke salt, $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ and $\text{Hg}[\text{Zn}(\text{CNS})_4]$; 27 for Cu(II) dithiocarbamate and 28 for Zn(II) dithiocarbamate and Zn(II) xanthate.

It may be noted that hydrazino nitrogen is oxidised to molecular nitrogen, whereas amino nitrogen is unaffected. Thiocyanate is oxidised to sulphate and cyanide. Sulphide is oxidised to elemental sulphur while sulphur in the other sulphur compounds is oxidised to sulphate. In the cases of Cu(II) sulphide and Cu(II) dithiocarbamate the numbers of equivalents of oxidant consumed per mole of the reductant are diminished by one each. That is, the equivalents obtained are 1 and 27 against the expected values of 2 and 28 respectively for CuS and Cu(II) dithiocarbamate. This is because copper being in the +2 oxidation state produces one equivalent of iodine with KI in the iodometric titrations adopted for the present method.

Typical results for the four types of titrations reveal that the methods are very accurate (error is always within $\pm 0.50\%$) and convenient. All the four methods are suitable for the determinations over wider concentration ranges, covering macro and semimicro levels. The concentration ranges studied here are 0.01-1.35 M moles.

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